

Securing IMF from Intent Injection Using BERT-Based Classifiers

Seonghyun Kim

Ericsson Research, Sweden
kim.seonghyun@ericsson.com

Abstract—Intent-based systems empower autonomous networks to operate based on high-level declarative goals, offering flexibility, scalability, and reduced operational complexity. While the security implications of such systems are recognized, intent injection attacks, which adversaries manipulate syntactically valid but semantically malicious intents, have remained largely theoretical due to the lack of standardized intent samples for empirical evaluation. This paper presents a semantic-level injection detection framework that employs a fine-tuned BERT classifier to transform each intent into a natural language representation. This enables semantic analysis of the intent’s content and classifies it as either benign or injected. To bridge the gap of unavailable real-world data, we synthesize training samples guided by benign and adversarial intent policies. For evaluation, we use intent samples from the recently released ETSI 3GPP TS 28.312 specification, creating variants by injecting code into their YAML structures to preserve structural validity while altering semantic meaning. Experimental results show that the proposed method effectively detects injected intents, achieving an AUC of 0.98 and an F1-score of 0.97, significantly outperforming existing injection detection methods such as PromptGuard and VulBERT, which prove ineffective against these attacks. These results underscore the necessity of developing tailored detection mechanisms for intent-based systems and highlight the potential of semantics-aware approaches to address this unknown known security threats.

Index Terms—Mobile communication, Communication system security, Classification algorithms

I. INTRODUCTION

An intent is a declarative information object that defines the requirements that an autonomous system and infrastructure are expected to fulfill. The receiving system is not instructed to perform a particular action or process. Instead, the system is free to choose a solution strategy autonomously.

Intent-based systems are becoming foundational in AI-driven networking [1]. In these architectures, high-level declarative intents are submitted through standardized APIs, for example, specifying that *the average throughput for users of a service must be higher than 100 Mbps*. Once accepted, the intent triggers a series of autonomous processes executed by internal modules, such as the Intent Management Function (IMF), without requiring detailed procedural instructions. These modules dynamically assess the current network state, select appropriate strategies, and coordinate execution across the management layers. For instance, as illustrated in Figure 1, the hierarchy of IMFs enables intent-driven automation across multiple layers. Each layer functions as both a client and a provider, processing intents through standardized interfaces

while enforcing domain-specific policies. This paradigm significantly enhances the scalability, flexibility, and responsiveness of complex systems by enabling intelligent operations within predefined policy boundaries.

While the flexibility and autonomy of these systems further enhance dynamic interactions and scalable operations, they may also introduce previously unrecognized security challenges. This paper explores this concern in intent-based systems: the possibility of intent injection vulnerabilities. Throughout this paper, intent injection refers to a class of attacks in which an adversary modifies intents that are syntactically correct and structurally valid, but are semantically crafted with malicious intentions.

Fig. 1: Intent Injection Attack Examples

Motivation: Injection attacks remain among the most persistent and damaging cybersecurity threats, consistently ranked as high-risk by major organisations such as OWASP [2]. These attacks exploit gaps in input validation to manipulate system behavior, where attackers craft malicious inputs to manipulate backend query execution, often leading to system compromise.

Intent-based networking introduces an intent, where operators specify what the system should achieve rather than how to achieve it. This shift has the potential to create a separation between syntactic structure and semantic meaning, which may open up new opportunities for injection style attacks that exploit this gap.

Intent injection threats, a class of injection attack that specifically targets intents within the context of intent-based networking, can be classified as an *unknown known* threat. Although the general risks of injection attacks are well understood (*known knowns*) and the security implications of intent-based systems are acknowledged [3], to the best of our knowledge, intent-level compromise has largely been treated as a hypothetical issue and remains a theoretical concern.

This is largely due to the lack of real-world intent samples, however, examples and grammars for intents have recently been formalized in standards, such as 3GPP TS 28.312 [4].

While existing injection defenses might appear applicable, many are designed to detect syntactic anomalies or rely on known attack patterns. As such, they may not extend well to semantically manipulated but structurally valid inputs, such as those found in 3GPP-style declarative intents. This poses specific challenges, particularly when attackers exploit semantics in task-specific or domain-specific ways.

In light of these considerations, there is a need to investigate detection methods tailored to intent-based networking, capable of analyzing the semantic content of structured inputs and identifying adversarial manipulations before they affect system behavior.

Contribution: This paper presents the first empirical analysis of intent injection threats within 3GPP autonomous management frameworks. By collecting the complete set of benign intent examples from the latest TS 28.312 specification, we provide the first evaluation instances for assessing security vulnerabilities in standardized intent formats. We further evaluate the performance of existing injection detection methods against this threat, revealing intent injection as a cold-start anomaly detection problem where existing methods fall short. To proactively address this challenge, we propose a semantics-aware detection method that integrates a fine-tuned BERT classifier with synthetic data generation, enabling the development of effective detection strategies in the absence of extensive real-world malicious intent injection datasets.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work. Section III formulates the threat. Section IV describes our detection methodology. Section V presents our experimental results. Section VI concludes the paper and describes directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORKS

Classic injection threats such as SQL injection [2] and SPARQL injection [5] have led to numerous defensive strategies, including SQLrand [6] and CANDID [7], which primarily rely on structural validation and syntactic correctness to ensure that inputs conform to expected formats. However, these defenses often operate at the surface level, focusing on syntactic correctness rather than semantics.

To address this issue, more recent research has focused on integrating semantic analysis into injection detection. Sania [8] combines syntactic and semantic analysis for SQL injection testing, while DeepSQLi [9] leverages semantic learning to model and detect malicious attacks injected in SQL queries. The increasing availability of pre-trained large language models (LLMs), such as BERT [10], has also enabled broader semantic understanding. Tools like PromptGuard [11] and VulBERT [12] use these models to identify injection risks in natural language prompts or code fragments. However, although these methods demonstrate progress, they are generally tailored to specific input formats, for instance, SQL code or prompts.

While intent-based networking is also expected to rely on structured declarative inputs in YAML as in 3GPP or similar

formats, it remains unclear how applicable existing methods are to this context. This paper explores whether synthetic sample approach [13], [14] can aid injection detection, offering early insights into its feasibility and limitations in this cold start anomaly detection problem [15].

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION: INTENT INJECTION ATTACKS

Similar to the known injection threats, we assume an injection adversary with access to the system’s intent submission interface either directly (e.g., through an exposed API) or indirectly (e.g., via a compromised tool or middleware). The adversary is not able to bypass authentication or encryption, and does not have direct control over internal IMF logic or databases, as well as no access to internal logs, execution traces, or the final resolution of the intent by the network system.

However, they are able to submit syntactically valid intents, or modify existing intents in transit, such as through misconfigured proxy layers, intent aggregators, or during operator-assisted orchestration. Such attacks do not require breaking authentication, transport security, or exploiting implementation bugs, but instead exploit the system’s inability to reason about the intent’s true purpose at the semantic level. This underscores the need for semantic-layer defenses that go beyond syntax-based checks.

It is important to distinguish intent injection detection from intent conflict detection. Both aim to identify unexpected network behavior; however, intent injection detection specifically seeks to detect intentional policy violations, in a manner similar to detecting distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks rather than identifying misconfigurations or software bugs. Our objective is to detect malicious or adversarial intents with minimum false-positive rates, rather than detecting benign but conflicting ones. In this context, we define malicious intent as any injected intent that deviates from the system’s defined policy. One particularly critical category of intent injection selected for this study is code injection and command injection, due to its high potential to compromise system stability, performance, and security.

A. Benign Behavior

Let \mathcal{X} denote the space of user-issued intents, where each $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is a structured management request in a declarative format such as YAML. Let $\mathcal{Y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_K\}$ represent the set of possible system behaviors or responses that may be triggered by an intent.

We model the system’s intent interpretation process as a function $f_\theta : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, parameterized by θ . This function maps each intent to a semantic category or behavioral label, which may subsequently drive automated decisions or trigger system-level responses.

Given a benign intent $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the system interprets it as:

$$\hat{y} = f_\theta(x) = \arg \max_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} p_\theta(y | x) \quad (1)$$

where $p_\theta(y | x)$ denotes the model’s confidence in mapping x to behavior y . Since the output of f_θ may directly influence

network operations, incorrect interpretations can result in unintended or unsafe behavior.

B. Adversarial Objective

In an intent injection scenario, the adversary crafts a modified intent $x' = A(x)$ using an injection function $A : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ that preserves syntactic validity while altering the semantic meaning. The adversary aims to induce a specific system behavior y_{target} , such that:

$$\text{Success}(x, A(x)) = \mathcal{I}[f_{\theta}(A(x)) = y_{\text{target}} \wedge f_{\theta}(x) \neq y_{\text{target}}] \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{I} equals 1 when the attacker's injected intent $A(x)$ makes the system f_{θ} responses the chosen target behavior y_{target} , even though the same system does not response the same behavior on x .

The adversarial objective is to maximize success over the input distribution:

$$\max_{A \in \mathcal{H}} \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{X}} [\text{Success}(x, A(x))] \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{H} denotes the set of feasible injection functions, i.e., transformations $A : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ that satisfy structural validity, subject to the following constraints:

- **Semantic plausibility:** the modified input maintains plausible meaning, measured by a semantic score $s(A(x)) \geq \tau$, where $s(\cdot)$ is a coherence or plausibility function (e.g., derived from language model perplexity or entailment confidence) and τ is the minimum semantic coherence, ensuring not being flagged trivially by a parser or validator.
- **Perturbation constraint:** the injected intent remains close to the original input, $d(x, A(x)) \leq \epsilon$, where $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a distance metric (e.g., edit distance or embedding similarity) and ϵ is the maximum allowed perturbation, ensuring the injection remains subtle.

These constraints model realistic adversarial settings where injected intents must remain plausible and avoid detection.

C. Defender Objective

The defender's goal is to construct a robust detection mechanism $D : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ that detects injected intents without significantly impacting benign operations. Formally:

$$D(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \text{ is an injected intent} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The objective is to minimize classification error:

$$\min_D \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{X}} [\ell(D(x), \text{label}(x))] \quad (5)$$

where $\text{label}(x) \in \{0, 1\}$ denotes the true class and ℓ is a loss function.

A key challenge in detecting intent injection lies in the semantic flexibility of structured inputs. Intents are often high-level and declarative, meaning structurally valid inputs $x \in \mathcal{X}$ can encode different behaviours. An adversarial modification

$A(x)$ may satisfy structural constraints $d(x, A(x)) \leq \epsilon$ and $s(A(x)) \geq \tau$, yet induce a behavioral shift in the model $f_{\theta}(x) \neq f_{\theta}(A(x))$. Existing injection defenses, which rely on known patterns, may overlook such subtle manipulations.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION: BERT-BASED DETECTION

Fig. 2: The Proposed Semantics-Aware Detection

To mitigate this potential threat in autonomous intent-based systems, we propose a detection framework based on a fine-tuned BERT classifier, which operates on natural language representations of structured intents. The architecture of our framework, illustrated in Figure 2, consists of two main components: (1) the semantic detector, which performs sequence classification on transformed intent texts, and (2) the synthetic data generator, which creates labeled training data from benign and injection policy definitions. Unlike conventional approaches that rely directly on input format structures, our method transforms structured intents into natural language representations, enabling more robust semantic analysis.

The detector processes incoming intents through a three-stage pipeline: (1) **Intent-to-Language Conversion** transforms structured intent data into natural language text, preserving semantic meaning while enabling NLP-based analysis; (2) **Sequence Classification** analyzes the converted text using fine-tuned BERT models to identify potential injection patterns and malicious intent modifications; and (3) **Decision** applies a classification threshold to determine whether an intent contains injected elements. The pseudocode for this proposed detection pipeline is detailed in Algorithm 1.

The synthetic data generator leverages a LLM to synthesize training data guided by following two policies: (1) **Benign Policy** defines the characteristics of legitimate intents, establishing patterns for normal system operations; and (2) **Injection Policy** specifies patterns that constitute malicious intent modifications. Using these policies as guidelines, the LLM synthesizes a balanced labeled dataset with both benign and injection labels, ensuring sufficient coverage of potential attack vectors for effective classifier training in the absence of real-world labeled data.

A. Detection via Sequence Classification

Intent-to-Language Conversion: Given that intents are specified in non-natural languages, the first step involves

converting structured intent commands into natural language. Formally, we define a conversion function $\psi : X \rightarrow T$, which maps a structured intent $x \in X$ into a natural language representation $t \in T$, making the input suitable for semantic analysis by language models. The specific prompt format used for this conversion is shown in Table I.

System Prompt:

You are a helpful assistant. The following is context from a document: {context}.

User Prompt:

Your job is to analyze a content and to look for whether there is unusual values or patterns across the content that might suggest code injection.
{intent}.

Analyse the above text and always response in plain sentences in the following format:

Intent Description: ...

Action: ...

Target: ...

Expectation: ...

Finding: ...

Only provide the formatted intent block.

TABLE I: Intent-to-Language Conversion Prompt

Sequence Classification: The natural language representation $t \in T$ is mapped into the BERT input space via a tokenizer $\varphi : T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, producing an embedding sequence vector $x_{\text{emb}} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The encoded representation x_{emb} is then passed to a fine-tuned BERT-based classifier $f_{\theta} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ which outputs a vector of class logits $z = [z_0, z_1]$, corresponding to the classes *benign* and *injected*, respectively. These logits are transformed into probabilities using the softmax function:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(z_i)}{\exp(z_0) + \exp(z_1)} \quad \text{for } i \in \{0, 1\},$$

where $z = f_{\theta}(x_{\text{emb}})$. The predicted intent label is given by:

$$y = \arg \max_i p_i.$$

Decision: Following the probability estimation, the detector applies a threshold-based decision rule. Let p_{injected} denote the predicted probability that the input corresponds to an injected intent. If $p_{\text{injected}} \geq \tau$, where $\tau \in [0, 1]$ is a predefined threshold, the intent is classified as *injected* and rejected. Otherwise, it is classified as *benign* and accepted.

B. Synthetic Training Data Generator

Given the absence of publicly available datasets for intent injection attacks, we adopt a fully synthetic data generation approach to construct a labeled training set suitable for classification. Our objective is to generate both benign and injection examples that reflect the types of attacks a intent-based system might encounter. We employ a LLM to generate synthetic training samples encompassing both benign and injected behaviors. The policy modules contain predefined operational and security rules that define acceptable behaviors and configurations within the network. These serve as the basis for generating training samples during training.

Algorithm 1: Intent Injection Detection via Semantic Classification

Input: Structured intent $x \in X$

Output: Detection result $D(x) \in \{0, 1\}$, probability vector $p \in [0, 1]^2$

```

1 Parameters:
2  $\psi : X \rightarrow T$  // Intent-to-language conversion
3  $\varphi : T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$  // Tokenizer
4  $f_{\theta} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$  // Classifier over  $Y = \{[1, 0], [0, 1]\}$ 
5  $\tau \in [0, 1]$  // Detection threshold

6 Step 1: Intent-to-Language Conversion
7  $t \leftarrow \psi(x)$  // Language representation

8 Step 2: Sequence Classification
9  $x_{\text{emb}} \leftarrow \varphi(t)$  // Tokenize and embed
10  $z \leftarrow f_{\theta}(x_{\text{emb}})$  // Logits  $z \in \mathbb{R}^2$ 
11  $p \leftarrow \text{softmax}(z)$  // Probabilities  $p = [p_{\text{benign}}, p_{\text{injection}}]$ 

12 Step 3: Decision
13 if  $p_{\text{injection}} \geq \tau$  then
14   return  $D(x) \leftarrow 1, p$  // Accepted
15 else
16   return  $D(x) \leftarrow 0, p$  // Rejected

```

Policy-to-Language Conversion: To generate natural language representations of policy rules, we employ a causal language model that translates structured policies into human-readable intent expressions. This submodule ensures that the resulting texts mimic the types of user-submitted or attacker-submitted intents that an intent-based system might encounter. The prompts used to elicit these completions are crafted to simulate either compliant or adversarial behavior, depending on the underlying policy type, as illustrated in II. This procedure ensures that both *benign* and *injected* samples are generated under uniform stylistic and contextual conditions, thereby reducing distributional biases during model training.

Each generated sample is labeled according to its originating policy: *benign* if derived from the benign policy, and *injected* if from the injection policy. The final dataset, consisting of natural language intent expressions with their corresponding labels, is then used to fine-tune a BERT-based sequence classification model.

System Prompt:

You are a helpful assistant. The following is context from a document: {context}.

User Prompt:

Your job is generating a synthetic example of intent.

Make sure the output only one intent in the following format:

Intent Description: ...

Action: ...

Target: ...

Expectation: ...

Finding: ...

Reflect the finding if you find any usual patterns.

Only provide the formatted intent block. Do not repeat the input content.

Your job is generating a synthetic example of intent following instructions:

{policy}

TABLE II: Policy-to-Language Conversion Prompt

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To systematically evaluate the robustness of our proposed method against both benign and injected inputs, we design a series of experiments comparing our approach with the following setup. The experiments were conducted using PyTorch as the machine learning framework. For the BERT-based classifier fine-tuning, we used the bert-base-uncased model [10]. For the causal models, we used the DeepSeek-R1 32B model [16]. As the system prompt context, we selected the first 6,000 words from the 3GPP TS 28.312 document [4], constrained by the language model’s system prompt token limit.

Baseline: As this is the first work that introduces intent injection attacks, no prior defense mechanisms exist for this threat yet. Therefore, we evaluate our method against a proxy baseline adapted from similar research in vulnerability detection. We adapt Prompt-Guard-86M (PromptGuard) [11], which is a Llama-based classifier originally developed for detecting prompt injections and jailbreaks, and VulBERTa-MLP-Deign (VulBERT) [12], which is a BERT-based classifier originally developed for detecting security vulnerabilities in source code. Both PromptGuard and VulBERT are trained to detect anomalies that may indicate unsafe or malicious behaviors. Having unexpected manipulations of structured input involved, they serve as a proxy for intent-level anomaly detection.

Fine-tuning Data: We defined two sets of policy definitions to generate the training set:

Benign Policy:

Represents valid configuration entries. No executable patterns.
Fields use static data (strings, numbers, booleans, or sets).
Avoid anything that looks like a code snippet.

Injection Policy:

Represents suspicious or dangerous patterns, such as:
- Embedded code snippets in values or descriptions.
- Patterns indicating a misuse of configuration to express program logic.
Use the following phrases that suggest suspicion or findings:
- Unusual pattern found. Executable logic detected.
- Possible code injection. Unexpected logic structure.

TABLE III: Policy Definitions for Synthetic Training Data

Each policy was used in the Policy-to-Language Conversion prompt, presented in Table II. In total, 750 benign and 750 injected intents were synthesized for the classifier fine-tuning.

Evaluation Data: Likewise, neither enough number of benign samples nor attack samples available. As for the first exploration of proof of concept, we constructed an evaluation dataset consisting of both benign and injected intent samples. We adopted the management intents defined in the 3GPP specification [4] as the foundation for benign examples. We selected all available sample intents (D.1 to D.11 except D.8) from Annex D of the specification. These represent valid, well-formed management, and benign intents used in autonomous network scenarios. To construct injection intents for evaluation, we created three categories of adversarial intent samples by injecting logic-based code fragments or command lines. We include Prolog due to its structural similarity to logic-based query constructs, such as those found in SPARQL injection attacks. While not natively part of SPARQL, Prolog serves as

a representative logic programming language to approximate injection patterns in such contexts. For each benign intent, we randomly select a `targetValueRange` attribute which is a critical parameter representing the desired value range in the intent specification, and replace its value with for each following injection:

- **Bash command:** `curl -X POST example.com,`
- **SQL code:** `SELECT user FROM user_table WHERE id=admin AND password=" " OR 1 = 1;`
- **Prolog code:** `loop_entry(N, A) :- N > 0, succ(N0, N), succ(A, A1), loop_entry(N0, A1).`

Each injected intent maintains the same structure as its benign counterpart, except for a single modification in the `targetValueRange` field. We repeat it five times for injection samples. This resulted in 150 ($= 10 \times 5 \times 3$) injected intents in total. In case of benign samples, run the solution and baselines five times, in other words, we run five times on Intent-to-Language for the solution, which resulted in 50 ($= 10 \times 5$) language representations for benign intents. For the baselines, we run five times for each benign intent.

Evaluation Method: We evaluate the detection performance of our proposed method and several baseline models using the receiver-operating characteristic (ROC) curve as well as its area under the curve (AUC). We further evaluate the detection performance of our proposed method in an ablation study using standard classification metrics, including true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), false negatives (FN), and F1-Score. A sample is classified as positive if it is detected as an intent-injection attack; otherwise, it is classified as negative.

A. Detection Performance

Fig. 3: ROC Curves and AUC Values

Figure 3 shows the ROC curves and corresponding AUC values for our proposed method compared to the baselines, PromptGuard and VulBERT. The proposed approach achieves a notable AUC of 0.981, significantly outperforming PromptGuard (AUC = 0.673) and VulBERT (AUC = 0.590). The steep ascent of the ROC curve for the proposed method indicates a strong capacity to distinguish between benign and injected intents. In contrast, PromptGuard’s curve shows a gradual incline with limited separation power, while VulBERT’s performance is more constrained, with its curve closely aligning to the diagonal, suggesting a near-random classification. This performance gap reflects that other injection detectors designed for other input formats fail to generalize effectively to intent injection detection.

B. Effect of Intent-to-Language Conversion

Prompts	TP	TN	FP	FN	Prolog	SQL	Bash	F1-Score
FSFU	142	49	1	8	0.86	0.98	1	0.97
NSFU	135	47	3	15	0.72	1	0.98	0.94
FSNU	132	28	22	18	0.78	0.92	0.94	0.87
NSNU	112	31	19	38	0.42	0.94	0.88	0.80

TABLE IV: Performance Impact of Intent-to-Text Conversion

Table IV presents the impact of Intent-to-Language Conversion on classification performance across different prompting configurations, using 0.5 for the decision rule’s threshold. The proposed method, **FSFU**, which uses the full system prompt and the full user prompt (Table I) for the conversion. In comparison, the **NSFU** configuration uses the same full user prompt but omits the system prompt entirely, while the **FSNU** configuration uses the full system prompt but omits the user prompt, i.e., just query an intent to evaluate. Lastly, the **NSNU** configuration uses neither the system prompt nor the user prompt.

The FSFU achieves consistently superior results compared to other baselines. It yields the highest overall F1-score (0.97). The two mixed ablation settings exhibit different impacts. The NSFU (0.94) achieves slightly higher FP rate compared to the FSFU. In particular, while it performs similar to FSFU in SQL and Bash, but shows poor performance in Prolog compared to the FSFU. Whereas, the FSNU (0.87) shows in particular, it shows poor performance in FP. This divergence suggests that system prompt guidance primarily curbs spurious detection requiring intent concepts, while the user prompt primarily helps distinguish benign from malicious intents; without them, both error types spike. Lastly, the USNU (0.80) underperforms all other variants, confirming that omitting both system and user guidance severely degrades the model’s ability to detect injection attacks.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we explored the possibility of intent injection vulnerabilities and proposed a defense framework tailored to intent-based networking systems, using datasets derived from the 3GPP TS 28.312 specification. Our analysis highlights a potential threat vector in automation frameworks, which adversarially crafted intents can manipulate systems that execute user intents. To address this, we designed a defense framework utilizes a BERT-based intent classifier fine-tuned by a synthetic labeled dataset.

Experimental results confirm that the selected existing injection detection techniques are not directly applicable or effective in this setting, necessitating the preparation of intent-injection specific defense strategies. Notably, our findings show that the proposed method, which is a proof-of-concept relying on a fully synthetic training set, can provide effective protection against injected intents, when appropriately guided by context and prompt structures. Future work includes exploring broader injection attack patterns that reflect more diverse attack strategies. Incorporating deeper context modeling and reasoning over sequential or multi-intent constructs may further improve resilience against sophisticated attacks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 101135576 (INTEND).

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Mehmood, K. Kravevska, and D. Palma, “Intent-driven autonomous network and service management in future cellular networks: A structured literature review,” *Computer Networks*, vol. 220, p. 109477, Jan. 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2022.109477>
- [2] “The OWASP Top 10 - 03 Injection,” 2021. [Online]. Available: https://owasp.org/Top10/A03_2021-Injection/
- [3] I. Ahmad, J. Malinen, F. Christou, P. Porambage, A. Kirstädter, and J. Suomalainen, “Security in intent-based networking: Challenges and solutions,” in *2023 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 296–301.
- [4] 3GPP, “Management and orchestration; Intent driven management services for mobile networks, TS 28.312, version 19.1.0,” 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Tech. Rep.
- [5] J. Wielemaker and M. Hendricks, “Why it’s nice to be quoted: Quasiquoting for prolog,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1308.3941, 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1308.3941>
- [6] S. W. Boyd and A. D. Keromytis, “Sqlrand: Preventing sql injection attacks,” in *Applied Cryptography and Network Security: Second International Conference, ACNS 2004, Yellow Mountain, China, June 8-11, 2004. Proceedings 2*. Springer, 2004, pp. 292–302.
- [7] S. Bandhakavi, P. Bisht, P. Madhusudan, and V. Venkatakrishnan, “Candid: preventing sql injection attacks using dynamic candidate evaluations,” in *Proceedings of the 14th ACM conference on Computer and communications security*, 2007, pp. 12–24.
- [8] Y. Kosuga, K. Kono, M. Hanaoka, M. Hishiyama, and Y. Takahama, “Sania: Syntactic and semantic analysis for automated testing against sql injection,” in *Twenty-third annual computer security applications conference (ACSAC 2007)*. IEEE, 2007, pp. 107–117.
- [9] M. Liu, K. Li, and T. Chen, “Deepsqli: Deep semantic learning for testing sql injection,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.11728>
- [10] J. Devlin, M. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, “BERT: pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1810.04805, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>
- [11] S. Wan, C. Nikolaidis, D. Song, D. Molnar, J. Crnkovich, J. Grace, M. Bhatt, S. Chennabasappa, S. Whitman, S. Ding, V. Ionescu, Y. Li, and J. Saxe, “Cyberseceval 3: Advancing the evaluation of cybersecurity risks and capabilities in large language models,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.01605>
- [12] H. Hanif and S. Maffei, “Vulberta: Simplified source code pre-training for vulnerability detection,” in *2022 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 2022, pp. 1–8.
- [13] M. Sharma, M. Tong, J. Mu, J. Wei, J. Kruthoff, and et al., “Constitutional classifiers: Defending against universal jailbreaks across thousands of hours of red teaming,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.18837>
- [14] M. Wagenstetter, P. Gospodnetic, L. Bosnar, J. Fulir, D. Kreul, H. Rushmeier, T. Aicher, A. Hellmich, and S. Ihlenfeldt, “Synthetically generated images for industrial anomaly detection,” in *2024 IEEE 29th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–8.
- [15] T. Reiss, G. Kour, N. Zwerdling, A. Anaby-Tavor, and Y. Hoshen, “From zero to hero: Cold-start anomaly detection,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.20341>
- [16] DeepSeek-AI, “Deepseek-r1: Incentivizing reasoning capability in llms via reinforcement learning,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.12948>